

Testing the capability and performance of Claude Sonnet 4 on the GRE physics test

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ABSTRACT

As the use of artificial intelligence (AI) has become increasingly prevalent in K–12 and post-secondary education, we sought to benchmark the ability of large language models (LLMs) to solve complex problems and demonstrate critical thinking. In this manuscript, we tested the performance of Claude Sonnet 4, an LLM developed by Anthropic, on a publicly available 70-question GRE Physics practice examination. We hypothesized that Claude would correctly answer more than 90% of the questions. To test this, each question was submitted individually to the model, and responses were recorded and scored using the official answer key provided by the Educational Testing Service (ETS). Claude achieved 65 out of 70 correct responses, corresponding to a scaled score of 990, the maximum possible score. These results suggest strong performance of large language models in complex scientific problem-solving tasks.

INTRODUCTION

LLMs have shown the capacity to analyze complex problems in the field of theoretical physics (1). Novel technology in silicon chips allows for cloud-based processing and integration into many platforms (2). Even with advanced technologies, AI occasionally experiences shortcomings in information accuracy, propagating incorrect data. Previous research shows that while most common AIs made for general use are capable of simpler homework problems, more complex university-level problems are much more difficult for the engine to solve, with an

accuracy rate of 35-39% on problems in upper-division fields such as optics, electromagnetism, and thermodynamics (3).

New specialized physics LLMs, enhanced with quantum engines, however, are much more capable of problem analysis than software open to the public (4). In a technical report of ChatGPT 4.0 by OpenAI, the model's parent company, data shows the engine received a 4/5 on the AP Physics 2 exam in 2023 (5). The percentile is given as 70%, as 30% of test takers received a 4 or higher that year (5).

We hypothesized that over 90% of given questions would be answered correctly

by Claude. Scoring confirmed this, with 65 out of 70 questions (~93%, scaled score 990) correctly answered. On average, it is determined that a scaled score >750 will equate admission to a high-class graduate institution (8). Claude performed best in section 3 of the test, focusing on quantum mechanics and atomic physics with all questions answered correctly, and performed worst in section 1, focusing on classical mechanics with 12.5/14 questions correctly answered. These findings support previous results regarding the ability of consumer LLMs to solve and explain questions in advanced scientific domains.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We used Claude Sonnet 4, Anthropic's most advanced free model (12). Taking questions from form GR1775 offered online by ETS, we fed a screenshot of each question into Claude individually with no additional text. Claude's response was checked against the answer key, and the question was either marked correct (green) or incorrect (red) on the score tracker. Since Claude imposes a limit on the number of messages per chat, we started multiple new strings for the LLM to answer all 70 questions.

While scoring, we awarded partial credit on questions where Claude answered incorrectly but answered correctly when asked a second time. If both attempts were

answered incorrectly, those questions were marked fully incorrect. After checking all the model's answers, the correct answers were tallied up and checked against the score conversion sheet to find the total score. Claude answered 65/70 questions correctly, resulting in a 990. Anywhere between 62-70/70 correct answers is considered a 990.

RESULTS

In our study, we sought to find the accuracy and improvement of AI critical problem solving in physics compared to previous studies. We tested our hypothesis by inputting individual problems from the 70-question test into Claude and recording the answers. We utilized official GRE resources to determine correct versus incorrect answers and scoring. Out of three sections of college physics, Claude performed the worst in classical mechanics, scoring 12.5 out of 14 questions and the best in quantum mechanics and atomic physics with all 16/16 questions correctly answered (Figure 1). Category 2, electromagnetism was Claude's second most proficient content area, with 12.5/13 correct (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Claude performance compared with average percent correct by content area.

It is also important to note that not all questions on the test are organized into 1 of 3 content areas. The test is composed of 20% classical mechanics, 18% electromagnetism, 13% quantum mechanics, 10% atomic physics, 10% thermodynamics and statistical mechanics, 9% specialized topics, 8% optics and waves, 6% special relativity, and 6% laboratory methods (7).

After scoring, we did not find any correlation between Claude's performance and the mean performance of students. Each question on the assessment is given a number, indicating the percentage of test takers in the United States who answered the question correctly. We found that out of 17 questions with mean 20-30% accuracy, Claude was only marked off half a point on a single problem (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Comparison of average percent correct and Claude's performance across difficulty levels.

The GRE uses a score scaling system ranging from 280 (0 correct) to 990 (62-70 correct) (7). In our experiment, Claude received a 990, placing in the 99th percentile for test takers in the United States (8).

Claude not only provided an answer to the question given but also gave an in-depth explanation into the topic and the chosen answer (Figure 3a). On questions where it provided an incorrect answer, the explanation provided helped us find where the model made a mistake, giving further guidance towards its most proficient versus least proficient content areas (Figure 3a).

I need to find the speed of light in a material with a dielectric constant of 4.0.
 The speed of light in a material is related to the speed of light in vacuum by:
 $v = c/n$
 where:
 • v is the speed of light in the material
 • c is the speed of light in vacuum (3.0×10^8 m/s)
 • n is the refractive index of the material
 For a nonmagnetic material, the refractive index is related to the dielectric constant by:
 $n = \sqrt{\epsilon_r}$
 where ϵ_r is the relative dielectric constant.
 Given:
 • $\epsilon_r = 4.0$
 • $c = 3.0 \times 10^8$ m/s
 First, I'll find the refractive index:
 $n = \sqrt{4.0} = 2.0$
 Now I can find the speed of light in the material:
 $v = c/n = (3.0 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s})/2.0 = 1.5 \times 10^8$ m/s
 The answer is (C) 1.5×10^8 m/s.

Figure 3a. Example of a correct response generated by Claude for a problem involving light and dielectric constants.

DISCUSSION

The results of our experiment exceeded our hypothesis of >90% accuracy with an overall score of 93% (scaled 990) and success on challenging, graduate-level physics questions. We found that Claude struggled the most with classical mechanics-based questions with 89% accuracy in the content area. Through machine learning and user-training, Claude will demonstrate further proficiency, possibly showing a 100% accuracy rate in future studies.

LLM responses and analysis can be subjective depending on model versions and qualities of specific engines. For example, Claude demonstrates high ability in question analysis and creative writing, but does not support image or video generation, unlike ChatGPT, which supports a full arsenal of AI tasks, such as coding, synthesis, and image/video generation (9). ChatGPT lacks

specialization in one or a few subjects, resulting in variable responses.

Power and speed of LLMs are also variable due to server overload and reciprocally, search engine speed, since models scan the internet for data. It is also important to mention that we were not subscribed to Claude's paid subscription, Claude Pro, which allows higher usage allotments and better models.

The GRE exam is designed to be administered to determine proficiency in a full range of college-level physics prior to admission to a graduate institution (10). Along with physics, GRE is available in mathematics and psychology (11).

When a question was answered incorrectly, it was a result of incorrect synthesis on Claude's end. For example, the model would calculate a ratio incorrectly or make a mistake during analysis of the given details (Figure 3b).

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I need to find the ratio of the periods of two planetary systems using Kepler's Third Law.
Given information:
• System 1: planet orbits at radius a around a star
• System 2: planet orbits at radius 4a around a star that's 4 times more massive
• Need to find: T1/T2 (ratio of period of system 1 to period of system 2)
Kepler's Third Law states:
T2 ∝ r3/M
Or more precisely: T2 = (4π2/GM) * r3
This can be written as: T = 2πv(r3/GM)
For System 1:
T1 = 2πv(a3/GM)
For System 2:
• Orbital radius = 4a
• Stellar mass = 4M T2 = 2πv((4a)3/G(4M)) = 2πv(64a3/4GM) = 2πv(16a3/GM)
Now I'll find the ratio:
T1/T2 = [2πv(a3/GM)] / [2πv(16a3/GM)]
T1/T2 = v(a3/GM) / v(16a3/GM)
T1/T2 = v(a3/GM) * v(GM/16a3)
T1/T2 = v(a3/GM * GM/16a3)
T1/T2 = v(1/16)
T1/T2 = 1/4
The answer is (C) T1/T2 = 1/4.

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Figure 3b. Example of an incorrect response generated by Claude for an astrophysics and planetary systems problem.

It is common for LLMs to make small mistakes in detail, as their information can become clouded when advanced synthesis is ongoing.

Many AI companies have multiple models for consumers, all specializing in different abilities (12). For example, Claude

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offers Opus, Sonnet, and Haiku, all with different analysis and writing skills (12). For our study, Sonnet was the best at the time but is currently second to Opus. A future study could focus on additional models and tests, finding different results based on varying synthesis techniques.

In summary, LLMs are transforming scientific study with their advanced ability to synthesize questions. This provides a powerful tool in education and research, allowing convoluted questions to be thought through without human error. Although AI demonstrates significant promise in many fields of study, it will always have limitations when it comes to reasoning about philosophical concepts or unresolved questions in cosmology and science.

REFERENCES

- (1) Pan, Haining, et al. "Quantum Many-Body Physics Calculations with Large Language Models." *Communications Physics*, vol. 8, no. 1, 31 Jan. 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-025-01956-y>
- (2) Govea, Jaime, et al. "Optimization and Scalability of Educational Platforms: Integration of Artificial Intelligence and Cloud Computing." *Computers*, vol. 12, no. 11, 1 Nov. 2023, p. 223, www.mdpi.com/2545084, <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers12110223>.
- (3) FirstPrinciples. "AI Faces Tough Physics Exam: Challenges in AI Science Proficiency." FirstPrinciples, 9 July 2025, <https://www.firstprinciples.org/article/ai-faces-a-tough-physics-exam-new-benchmark-reveals-the-challenge> Accessed 3 Feb. 2026.
- (4) "IonQ | Supercharging AI with Quantum Computing: Quantum-Enhanced Large Language Models." [ionq.com](https://www.ionq.com), 2025, <https://www.ionq.com/blog/supercharging-ai-with-quantum-computing-quantum-enhanced-large-language>. Accessed 5 Feb. 2026.
- (5) OpenAI. GPT-4 Technical Report. OpenAI, 27 Mar. 2023.
- (6) Interpreting Your GRE® Scores: 2025–26, <https://www.ets.org/pdfs/gre/interpreting-gre-scores.pdf>. Accessed 05 Mar. 2026.
- (7) GRE ® Subject Test in Physics. <https://www.ets.org/pdfs/gre/practice-book-physics.pdf>. Accessed 12 Mar. 2026.
- (8) number2. "GRE Physics Subject Test - [2022 Scores, Tips & Strategies Explained] -." *Number 2*, 20 Feb. 2022, <https://www.number2.com/gre-physics> Accessed 13 Mar. 2026.
- (9) Kane, Ryan. "Claude vs. ChatGPT: What's the Difference? [2024]." Zapier.com, 16 July 2024, <https://www.zapier.com/blog/claude-vs-chatgpt/>.
- (10) "SAT vs. ACT, GRE vs. GMAT, SAT Subject Tests and the Percentile Paradox." [Mcelroytutoring.com](https://www.mcelroytutoring.com), 2026, <https://www.mcelroytutoring.com/blog-post.php?id=4072>. Accessed 20 Mar. 2026.
- (11) "GRE Subject Tests." Ets.org, 2023, <https://www.ets.org/gre/score-users/about/subject-tests.html#accordion-b2c7932074-item-6d8fe1bbcf>.
- (12) "Models Overview." Claude Docs, 2025, <https://platform.claude.com/docs/en/about-claude/models/overview>.